

THE ANALYSIS OF BINARY FEATURES IN JAPANESE

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The purpose of this paper is to understand the structure of binary features in Japanese, since definiteness can be explained by pointing out to the syntactic, semantic and featural aspects of the language. Even though the discussion includes privative, attributive features as well, we will confine this article to the problem of binary features. Different theories, models and approaches take different views on how features should be understood in Japanese in terms of whether features resemble labels or categories and what variation should be allowed within a single system of features as seen before

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A typical Japanese NP is formed out of a noun as the head of a phrase together with zero (\emptyset) or more dependent constituents of various types as it's adnominal. The relative position and order of a dependent adnominal is a typological parameter, on which an NP turns on. The adnominal constituents in an NP vary in structure and function, which are of four types: morphological, lexical, phrasal, and clausal, of which the morphological one tends to be a smaller, while the clausal one tends to be a larger one (Givon, 2001;1-3).

From this point of view, some may argue that syntactic phenomena in Japanese is hazardous. However, we deny this thesis and show that nominalization as a means of obtaining definite interpretation in Japanese is syntactically driven. For example, in this paper I will bring into discussion two types of nominalization that occur in Japanese, namely the lexical nominalization and the clausal nominalization as a relevant dichotomy.

The nominalization processes that operate on lexical forms are the grammatical processes of conversion and derivation at the lexical level, while those that operate on the sentences are dual processes of transformation and derivation and reduction in certain causal properties of clauses at the sentence level.

In this regard, we can derive different types of NMLs by investigating the nominalization processes operating over different kinds of NLZs with the support of necessary linguistic evidence (Chen, 2013). These grammatical processes are conversion and derivation which operate over the words other than the noun, i.e. verb and adjective at the lexical level and bring forth lexical NMLs.

Clausal nominalizations come as the result of the SOV structure of Japanese since they require noun as determinants. Additionally, one can derive Nominal clauses by investigating the dual processes of transformation, and derivation and reduction in certain clausal properties of clauses operating over the NLZs at the sentence with the support of linguistic evidence. In this phase, we accumulated all the yields of the nominalization including Lexical NMLs and ANCs, and Nominal clauses, which are as good as Noun and good enough to partake in the formation of NPs. Then, in the second, i.e. last phase, we showed how each of the lexical NMLs, ANCs, and nominal clauses either as a Head or

as an Adnominal partake in the formation of NPs with the support of linguistic data. The existence of both lexical and clausal nominalizations is an indication that nominalization represents a genuine linguistic process and is not hazardous.

Lexical nominalization is a productive process, by means of which a word belonging to other than the noun class yields a derivative noun as in the constituent with or without some morphological adjustment. It is relatively less productive in Japanese as compared to that in English. Nishio (1961) found only 30% -40% of verbs can be transformed into deverbal NMLs. Hanna (2018:43) offers a new analysis of Japanese nominalization that distinguishes between lexical and grammatical nominalizations on one hand, and between verbal-based nominalizations and nominal-based nominalizations on the other. Formal nouns like `koto` and `no` partake in this operation. These processes yield the Noun Phrase definite according to him:

(1) Sekai-no ugoki-o yomi nasai.

*N.World,PART.Gen.,N.Movement,PART.Acc.,V.I
MPER.Read*

Read the trends in the world.

(Horie, 1997:45)

(2) Gakubutchoo tosite-no sekinin-no omosa-o keikensita.

*N.School,N.Dean,PREP.Regarding,PART.Gen.,
N.Responsabil-
ity,PART.Gen.,N.Importance,PART.Acc.V.PAST.Ex
perienceI*

I experienced the importance of Dean's overall responsibility.

(Hanna, 2018:51)

(3) Nero-ga rooma-o hakai sita koto-wa zizitu-da.

*N.Nero,TOP.,N.Roma,PART.Acc.,N.Destruction,
V.PAST.Do,N.Thing,TOP.,N.Fact,V.Be*

Nero's destruction of Rome is a fact.

(Horie, 1997:48)

(4) yama-ni iku yori umi-ni iku hoo-ga ii

*N.Moun-
tain,PART.Dat.,V.Go,PREP.Than,N.Sea,PART.Dat.,V.
Go,TOP.,Adj.Good*

It is better to go to the sea than to go to the mountains.

(Horie, 1997: 51)

(5) *Ken wa [[Sai ga motte kita]NMLZ no]NP o tabeta.*

N.Ken, TOP., N.Sai, TOP., V.PAST.Bring, PART.NO M., PART.Acc., V.PAST.Eat

Ken ate what Sai brought.

(Hanna, 2018: 64)

In the examples above we notice an instance of a nominalizer being transformed into a Noun Phrase by means of the genitive particle `no` adjoining the accusative particle `o` which should have introduced the direct object clause.

Another interesting instance of lexical nominalizations is that which includes relative clauses. Even though some may argue against categorizing relatives as part of lexical nominalizations, they are classified as such by authors like Simpson (2003), who bring into discussion eloquent sentences.

This is mainly because relatives, as shown above, lack the relative pronoun and are obtained by means of adjoining two nouns or two clauses. This allows for lexical interpretation of the phenomenon under the process of nominalization. Even though relatives are already definite by nature, since they provide a plus of semantic content nominalizing them contributes even further to the definite character of the Noun Phrase. In Japanese it is well-known that subjects in relative clauses may appear in either nominative or genitive case, as in (6), this being commonly referred to as *ga/no* conversion:

(6) *Taroo-ga/-no katta hon.*

N.Taroo-NOM/-GEN, V:Past.Buy, N.Book

'the book that Taroo bought'

Some authors have tried to provide a syntactic foundation for this phenomenon, namely to prove that indeed lexical nominalizations are not hazardously formed, but they are part of a linguistic mechanism to render the syntagm definite, for example, to find restrictions (privative features) or any other sorts of principles that limit or allow the occurrence of lexical nominalizations within relatives. Simpson (2008:146) compared Korean to Japanese and found that in addition to the thematic 'possessor' restriction in modern Korean, it is also not possible for a genitive subject in modern Korean relative clauses to be preceded by an adverb such as *eccey* 'yesterday' which refers to the action of the relative clause, as in (7) (Shigeko, 1991:20). It is in sharp contrast to modern Japanese where a sentential adverb may precede a genitive subject, as shown in (8) (Matsumoto, 1997:6)

(7) [*eccey John-i/*John-uy sa-n*]-chayk

Adv.Yesterday, N.John-NOM/John-

GEN, V:Past.Buy-N, N.Book

'The book that John bought yesterday.'

(8) [*kinoo Hanako-no katta*] hon-wa Botchan desu

Adv.Yesterday, N.Hanako-

GEN, V:Past.Buy, N.Book-TOP, N.Botchan, V:Pres.Be

'The book which Hanako bought yesterday is Botchan.'

Previously however, this relation of the genitive DP to the relative clause head-noun/ NP appears to have been unrestricted, and it is clearly unrestricted in modern Japanese, so a natural question now is to ask how the un/restricted distinction between modern Korean and middle Korean/modern Japanese should be captured. One possible route of explanation in the analysis of Shibatani (2009) is to pursue the connection between gerund-type nominalizations and the occurrence of genitive subjects in relative clauses. This is seen in English gerunds and Korean type III gerund nominalizations and also in a number of nominalizations formed with *no* in Japanese, as for example in (9) and (10), (9) being a simple clausal nominalization, (10) a pseudo-cleft type structure also formed with the element *no* and allowing for optional genitive case:

(9) *Hanako-ga [Taroo-no tsuita] no-o mita Hanako-*

N.Hanako, NOM, N.Taroo-

GEN, V:Past.Arrive, NOM., ACC, V:Past.See

'Hanako saw Taroo arrive.'

(10) [*Taroo-no katta*] no-wa hon desu

N.Taroo-

GEN, V:Past.NOM., TOP., N.Book. V:Pres.Be

'What Taroo bought was a book.'

Simpson (2008) finds a second possible way of accounting for the unrestricted genitive case available for Japanese relative clause subjects which might be to suggest that when the posited attributive form nominalizer became re-analyzed into the tense system, the nominalizer position might not have simply disappeared but instead may have been retained and occupied by a new null nominalizer element. Elsewhere where the attributive form was re-analyzed and its hypothetical nominalizer status was lost, a new overt nominalizer was in fact inserted in a renewal process common in language development:

(12) [*te tataka-ba yamabiko-no kotauru*] ito urusai.

N.Hand, V.Clap-as, N.Echo-

GEN, N.Answer.ADN, Adv.Very, Adj.Annoying

'It is very annoying that there is an echo when he claps his hands.'

(Genji monogatari, 11thC)

(13) [*te-o tatau-to kodama-ga kotaeru*] no-wa taihen huyukai-da.

N.Hand-ACC., V.Clap, Prep.When, N.Echo-

NOM, V.Answer, NO-TOP, Adv.very Adj.Annoying, V.Pres.Be

'It is very annoying that there is an echo when he claps his hands.'

(Tsujimura, 2007:52)

The denotation of the *no*-headed part is determinate in two respects. Firstly, as shown in (40), it is de-

terminate with regard to the definiteness of the denotation, meaning that it renders the lexeme definite, turning it from adjective to noun. Secondly, it is determinate in that it shows syntactic restrictions. The example are borrowed from Seraku (2012:8):

- (14) [Akai no]-o Tom-ga nagu-tta.
[red NO]-ACC Tom-NOM hit-PAST
'Tom hit a/the red one.'

Makino (1968: p.51) observes that *no* cannot stand on its own. Compare (202) with (203):

- (15) * No-o Tom-ga nagu-tta.
NO-ACC Tom-NOM hit-PAST

Makino considers only participant nominalization, but it is also true of situation nominalization. (204) should be compared with (202).

- (16) * No-o Tom-ga shi-tteiru.
NO-ACC Tom-NOM know-PRES

4.2.3.1. Conclusions of This Section

Even though they lack Gender and Number, Japanese nouns have been shown to possess a number of

Even though we have already stated binary features cannot account for the definite status of a noun, there is an approximate characteristic and that is polarity. The lack of relative pronouns makes it necessary for linguists to understand which noun determines which noun. The polar noun is that which is determined and explained by a second noun in the relative clause. For this reason, Tenten (2019:34) argues that the polar Japanese noun bears definite interpretation, although this mechanism is somehow inaccurate in comparison to that proposed by privative features in the previous section.

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